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Transformation of the Indonesian Government Bureaucracy

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Abstract

The bureaucracy is an organ of government that intersects with society because, as a public servant, it meets the community's needs and interests. The conditions and interests of the organization are very dynamic, in line with the development of various dimensions of people's lives. Therefore, the government bureaucracy must be able to keep up with these changes, especially those related to speed and accuracy in the service process. Functions service through changing the attitude and perspective of the bureaucratic apparatus towards the functions and duties professionally, namely by strengthening the carrot and stick system and decentralizing authority. This study used a type of observational research. The data collection form with documents, observations, and in-depth interviews, the researcher tests credibility and conducts data analysis, including data reduction, data presentation, and drawing research conclusions. The research design used is a qualitative research method. All data were obtained using analysis in various related literature.

Keywords: Transformation, Public Service, Bureaucracy, Carrot, and Stick

1. Introduction

Indonesia's bureaucratic reform has entered the final road map. At the end of the 2020-2024 road map period, it is hoped that the achievement of world-class bureaucracy can be the answer to many problems, questions, or doubts about Indonesia's ability to realize superior human resources, as well as become the foundation of bureaucracy for the golden generation in 2045. Indonesia's golden generation 2045 will be achieved if there is a good and systematic development of human resources, which is characterized by the following characteristics: (1) having a comprehensive intelligence, namely productive and innovative, (2) being peaceful in social interactions and strong character, (3) healthy in natural interactions, and (4) superior (Oktari, 2020). This golden generation is predicted to reach 140 million by 2040. Human resource development is one of the efforts to respond to demographic bonuses and create opportunities and a generation of hard workers who have the ability and master technology so that they can compete globally. However, the golden generation in 2045 will only be realized if it is followed up by investing in human resource development (Kompas, December 27, 2017).

On the other hand, the Revolution of Industry 4.0 has disrupted various strategic environments of human life. These changes have not only a negative impact but also a positive one with the acceleration of the transition of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 to Society 5.0. For example, the acceleration of the use of Artificial Intelligent (AI) and its implementation in people's lives (Özdemir & Hekim, 2018); (Fukuyama, 2018). The presence of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 has also greatly influenced the organizational system of human work on earth, as Klaus Schwab argued. Schwab's argument states that the Industrial Revolution 4.0 has brought speed, breadth, and depth of systematic impact on countries, societies, industries, and enterprises (Schwab, 2016).

Similarly, the systemic impact of inequality as the most significant challenge will also emerge. At least Schwab's view predicts that the influence of this industrial revolution on the economic sphere will affect economic growth and the type and nature of work. It will affect consumer expectations in the business field, with better structuring of product types, collaborative innovation, and new operating models.

The presence of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 also introduces the procedures of an all-digital technology work system that has been proven to be widespread in various parts of the world (Fukuyama, 2018). An all-online work system, sharing economy, data integration, and the use of technological application systems and the like have changed the behavior of governance services in government management. The governance of government management through the existing bureaucracy must certainly reposition itself so that it remains relevant in responding to increasingly demanding public demands (Firdaus et al., 2021). The strategy of transforming the bureaucracy to become more adaptive, agile, and fluid becomes a non-negotiable necessity (Holmqvist & Pessi, 2006).

Inevitably and delayed again, Indonesia must also leapfrog towards a digital-based government. The development of digitalization in several countries in the private and public sectors has been very rapid and connected to the demands of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Dumalang, 2021). This gave birth to Governance 4.0, a bureaucratic condition characterized by speed and convergence in all matters, both in government, development, and public services. On the other hand, the current characteristics of the Indonesian bureaucracy are still at the Governance 1.0 level, characterized by a high political orientation, overlapping various inter-agency programs and activities, and various manual and fragmented business processes. The current development of technological convergence provides an excellent opportunity for Indonesia to jump toward Governance 4.0. Can this happen? (Ismail, 2019)

There are some fundamental problems with a digital bureaucracy (Prasojo, 2021). First, the need for standard structure and metadata in the Indonesian bureaucracy. It creates different data structures for the same type of data so that it cannot be the basis of a single data for various decision-making processes, policies, and development programs/activities between government agencies. Integrating various development programs, government, and digital public services requires One Data Indonesia, which is accompanied by the regulation and management of security systems so that the data can be well protected and not easily hacked. The problem with current data is that data in various government application systems often creates redundancy, has different references, needs to be more accurate, and has a variety of standards. It creates confusion for every government agency in making development policies and programs, such as poverty reduction programs and programs to strengthen Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), which data are true and accurate. The variety of data today makes it challenging to build an integrated digital bureaucratic system between government agencies. In addition, the proliferating outsourcing pattern in creating various applications and their maintenance causes potential threats to data sovereignty and security because they are prone to leakage by third parties and, of course, high dependence on third parties.

The second is the utilization of technology that still needs to be more cohesive. Government agencies make many applications for various purposes of government administration. Of course, this also creates duplication and difficulty in integrating the provision of services. For the staffing system, approximately 27,000 applications and staffing databases are currently spread across 2,700 government-owned server rooms.

The third is the low sustainability of the application because its development needs to follow the standards of technology and good management, resulting in the application becoming digital waste and prone to hacking. The root of the problem is the need for standard management business systems and processes so that each government agency builds its technological system based on its respective understandings and needs. On the other hand, in many local governments, the business processes of internal management (such as staffing, planning, assets, and public services) are still carried out manually based on physical documents and are rigid.

The transformation of the bureaucracy towards dexterity and high power with an increasingly fluid work structure through a result-oriented matrix work organization model is the answer to respond to the demands of an increasingly demanding society. This bureaucratic transformation is essential amid general bureaucratic conditions that are still not conducive to the development of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, where a rigid bureaucracy still confines us due to the application of regulations, procedures, hierarchies, and controls as the basis of the Weberian bureaucracy (Serpa & Ferreira, 2019). The hierarchical and concentrated Weberian bureaucratic model, with decision-making power resting with the top leadership, also often makes the decision-making process sluggish. By experts, such a disease is often referred to as time lag or decision-making delay, which is the time lag between the formulation of a policy and its implementation (Jovanovski & Muric, 2011). Therefore, bureaucratic transformation to be more adaptive, agile, and fluid is becoming increasingly relevant amid the torrent of revolution of the 4.0 industry with its various disruptions. In addition, the momentum of the Covid-19 pandemic should encourage its acceleration, primarily by building a conducive ecosystem that can answer various existing challenges. The transformation of bureaucratic organizations requires collaboration and synergy built horizontally and vertically in each government agency. Another thing that is no less important is to change the way of working, culture, and thinking (mindset) so that later bureaucratic organizations can be more adaptive, agile, and fluid in providing excellent service.

2. Problem

With the increasing public demands on bureaucratic services, bureaucracy is often positioned negatively with inaction, inefficiency, and even manipulation. So what is essential to be the main point of attention is how to carry out bureaucratic transformation so that public servants' main functions and duties are realized.

3. Purpose

This study aims to analyze the transformation of the Indonesian bureaucracy and whether it has carried out its main functions and duties as a public servant.

4. Research Methods

This study used a type of observational research—data collection with documents, observations, and in-depth interviews. The researcher tests credibility and conducts data analysis, including data reduction, data presentation, and drawing research conclusions. The research design used is a qualitative research method, and all data were obtained using analysis in various related literature. According to (Creswell, 2009), qualitative research methods are based on postpositivism, philosophy, which is used to research scientific conditions in which the researcher himself is the instrument, data collection techniques, and qualitative analysis puts more emphasis on meaning.

Qualitative research methodology aims to analyze and describe phenomena or objects of research through social activities, attitudes, and perceptions of people individually or in groups. The theoretical foundation is used as a guide so that the research focuses on the facts in the field. In addition, this theoretical basis is also helpful in providing an overview of the research background and as material for discussing research results. The data analysis technique used in this study is a narrative analysis technique that focuses on how an idea or story is communicated to related parts. This research is expected to get results that can be used to solve a related problem. The type of approach to this research is descriptive. Descriptive research seeks to tell the solution to existing problems based on data.

5. Literature Reviews

In a country, bureaucracy is needed as a means of administration that can improve people's performance. Bureaucratic procurement is expected to help the community meet life's needs and get convenience in government services. According to Sawir (2020), in the book *Public Service Bureaucracy: Concepts, Theories, and Applications*, etymologically, bureaucracy is taken from the word "bureau" in French and "Kratos" in Greek. "Bureau" means writing desk, while "Kratos" means government. The bureaucracy is a group working behind a desk in offices or the government sector.

When viewed in politics or government, bureaucracy is defined as the embodiment of the state government apparatus in carrying out and implementing various policies through predetermined stages.

Some leading experts conveyed the definition of bureaucracy according to him. Here is the explanation: Max Weber. In the journal *Strategic Management of Bureaucracy in the Era of Disruption* by Risnawan (2018), it is written that Max Weber defines bureaucracy as a form of organization whose application is appropriate or related to the common goal to be achieved. It means that bureaucracy is used to organize work regularly.

Fritz Morstein Marx. According to Fritz Morstein Marx, the definition of bureaucracy is a type of organization that the current government commonly uses to carry out tasks of a specialist nature, performed by the government apparatus in an administrative system.

Blau and Page. As quoted from the book *Bureaucracy (Study of Concepts, Theory towards Good Governance)* by Muhammad (2018), Blau and Page explained bureaucracy as a type of organization used to carry out large administrative tasks, coordinating the work of many people systematically or regularly.

Dwijowijoto. The definition of bureaucracy, according to Dwijowijoto, is an institution that is very strong with the ability to increase potential capacity for good and evil, whose existence is as a neutral, rational administrative instrument.

One of the main characteristics of bureaucracy is that it is usually used by large organizations, such as the government, and is formal. In addition to these characteristics, the bureaucracy has several other characteristics: (1) The work is rigorous and regulatory-oriented. (2) The task is a specialization or particular or specific. (3) It is usually rigid and straightforward. (4) The implementation shall be conducted officially or formally. (5) Be central or centralized. (6) It usually follows the agreed terms. (7) The form is structured. It means having precise organizational makeup. (8) Obey and comply with existing rules or regulations. (9) The existence of hierarchical authority vertically. (10) Sometimes, the service procedures could be more precise, making decision-making difficult.

Types of Bureaucracy Bureaucracy is divided into three types: (1) General government bureaucracy Is a series of government organizations that carry out general government tasks. This task is more of a regulative function or regulating nature—for example, the field of order and security. (2) Development bureaucracy Is a series of governmental organizations with specific or specific duties. The purpose of this task is to achieve the goals of community development. Examples include agriculture, health, education, and industry. (3) Service bureaucracy Is a series of governmental organizations related to society. Its primary function is to provide services to the community. For example, public services (making ID cards) and passport processing. Examples of bureaucracy we can meet in everyday life. Local government is a form of bureaucracy in the field of the general government. Another example is hospitals and schools, as a form of bureaucracy in the development field, alternatively like the Department of Population and Civil Registry, which is a form of bureaucracy in the service field.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Bureaucracy As Public Servants

In modern government, the position of the bureaucracy as a public servant becomes an essential measure of the government's success in the eyes of the public. It is a common opinion that government agencies that serve the community's interests are often identified with inaction, difficulties, or other negative terms because it is complicated to get services that are by the community's needs. The functions carried out by the government are different from the private sector because the function of government services in meeting the interests of the community cannot be carried out by other organizations, especially market-oriented organizations that will eventually create injustice. According to Supriatna, the central and local bureaucracy must have three critical aspects in the process of development and service to the people. The three essential aspects are (Supriatna, 1997, p. 104): First, having a high responsibility as a servant of the state and a servant of the community. Second, it is responsive to problems the community faces, especially those that require community services broadly. Third, commitment and consistency to the value of moral standards in exercising government power.

The opinion above expressly positions the importance of bureaucracy concerning society, and to realize the position proportionally requires awareness from the government bureaucracy. With a strategic position and determining the fulfillment of the needs and interests of the community, the government bureaucracy in carrying out its functions and duties as a public servant has characteristics, according to (Munier et al., 2019) as follows:

1. Services organized are more urgent than those organized by private agencies.
2. Services by the government generally have the nature of monopoly or semi-monopoly or semi-monopoly
3. Formal legal provisions bind the activities of government agencies.
4. Services by the government are not tied to market prices.
5. The government's deeds are carried out under the observation of the people.

The statement illustrates that the bureaucracy is responsible and obligated to provide services to society without discrimination against any member. Public service is an activity aimed at meeting the needs of the community. When viewed from the government side, service is nothing but a process of activities carried out by the government to meet the community's needs related to the rights possessed.

In essence, the provision of services to the community by the government has become the duty and responsibility of the government in realizing the services provided to the community (Ndraha, 2003: 78). The government functions primarily as a provider of non-privatized public services including defense and security services, and civil services, including bureaucratic services. These public and civil services are government monopolies because they concern the people's interests, and the monopoly is inseparable from its urgency from the point of view of public interest. So it can be categorized as the primary function of government, as stated by Ndraha (2003:78):

"Primary functions constantly run and are positively related to the power that is governed. The primary function never decreases with the increase in the empowerment of society—the more powerful the ruled, the more the primary function is ruled. The government primarily functions as a provider of public and civil services, including bureaucratic services, and both functions are abbreviated as service functions".

It is realized that there are community interests that other parties need help to meet. The bureaucracy, as a government organ, produces and distributes means of meeting the needs of the people in the form of public and civil services. To meet the needs, the government must provide services to the community to meet their needs. In essence, the provision of services to the community is not only carried out by the government. However, it can also be done by other private parties, producing services and services to the community. The private sector can meet the needs and interests of the community because the mechanisms in force in the market may need to be able to optimally, or, indeed, the government conditions it as such. The role of the government is to provide services with the primary objective of maintaining a system so that people can realize what they need. In

principle, fulfilling people's needs the government is a form of government responsibility to the community. The government is expected to have the ability to provide the best service to the community.

6.2. Adaptive, Agile, and Fluid

The concept of Agile governance or called agile government is a bureaucratic concept that has long been studied in academia, especially in the department of public service management or public administration. The advantage of this Agile concept or method is to simplify the bureaucracy and focus on speed and convenience as a manifestation of dynamic governance, the dialectic of changing state relations demands bureaucratic changes so as not to be eroded by the times (*obsolete*).

The concept of New Public Management, New Public Service, clean up, design thinking, Scrum method, and others is a form of agile adaptation and bureaucratic fluidity through ecosystem improvement of the government work system. It can answer the challenges of improving the quality of public services through ecosystem improvement. The adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucratic ecosystem no longer relies on top-down personalization, hierarchy, and strict decolonization. However, it is an ecosystem that can build a learning organization, develop strategic dialogue and public sector marketing, and support all HR (taking ownership) to achieve the shared vision.

Acceleration of bureaucratic reform is needed to lead to better governance characterized by an adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucratic system, with characteristics such as good governance, focus on services, community involvement in government, innovation, responsiveness, and result-oriented. As a form of acceleration, it is necessary to carry out the organizational transformation, including improving business processes, service quality, performance management, and supervisory system. It will undoubtedly run optimally supported by three pillars: digital capabilities, organizational culture, and innovation so that a world-class adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucracy can be realized. Significant changes to the bureaucratic work ecosystem must follow changes in the new work model by converting functional positions. This conversion is not limited to label changes but includes changes in how things work, building a new work ecosystem, and creating new KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).

The current Covid-19 pandemic should be used as a momentum for the State Civil Apparatus to prepare The New Normal in supporting the acceleration of adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucratic reforms so that bureaucratic organizations can play a role as a determinant factor in winning the global competition. We hope that in realizing an adaptive, agile, and fluid bureaucracy, there will be synergy and collaboration from the central and local governments and the commitment of all parties to change for the better. This new paradigm is expected to change the orientation of how to work to network government and collaborative governance. By prioritizing liquid collaboration, bureaucratic agility will be built with high responsiveness in increasing competitiveness so that bureaucratic reforms with an adaptive, agile, and fluid ecosystem can drive investment, create jobs, and ensure sustainable economic growth in delivering Golden Indonesia 2045. Increasingly has strategic value during the condition of the Indonesian nation, which is still struggling with the Covid 19 pandemic. Bureaucratic reform through adaptive, agile, and fluid governance of government bureaucratic organizations is the answer to the acceleration of Bureaucratic reform, which aims to increase the nation's competitiveness with a competitive culture by creating a more adaptive, agile, and fluid work organization ecosystem.

6.3. Indonesian Bureaucratic SuperApps

The leap of change toward Indonesia's Digital Bureaucracy must be forced through the development of SuperApps, an integrated digital platform that offers a wide range of services in one application. We envision integrating data, business processes, and technology for various purposes of internal government services and public services to the community. Can the transformation process from a manual, traditional and partial bureaucracy to a digitally integrated bureaucracy be carried out quickly? Of course, this can be done. First, because of the high commitment of the President of the Republic of Indonesia, Joko Widodo, and Vice President Ma'ruf Amin, as stated on various occasions. Second, that technology is both a force tool of change and an

enabler in the process of change itself. Furthermore, third, the development of various digital services in the private sector (online shopping) has awakened and provided evidence of the convenience and efficiency obtained through technology. Of course, the way of thinking must be developed digitally and dynamically, not analog, step-by-step, and linear.

With the Indonesian bureaucratic SuperApps, various government business processes and services must be reorganized immediately. The realignment of business processes within agencies and between agencies is carried out with various reregulation and deregulation of regulations by the need to integrate data and systems of the S-based applicationuperApps. It is necessary to immediately build a National Data Center to become a home for One Data Indonesia. Also, build information and communication technology (ICT) sharing, and prepare machine learning and artificial intelligence technology that will be used for big data analytics as a basis for various decision-making needs and development policies. With the Indonesian bureaucratic SuperApps, various public services can be carried out online integrated with one hand, just like people in the general shop online through various applications that can be downloaded and used at any time via cellular phones.

In addition to being more efficient and effective, online services through SuperApps will prevent various potential corruption that has occurred so far through face-to-face meetings and various manual physical data that can be lost or manipulated. Based on microservices and multiplatform technology, various public service applications can be added gradually and continuously within SuperApps. On the other in, the bureaucracy will also be more flexible to be carried out anywhere and anytime with quality assurance based on an integrated and standardized system. It is possible to do this because, at this time, the number of millennials (Y, Z) has reached 31 percent, and in 2024 it has reached 42 percent; that is, a generation that is very familiar with and accustomed to interacting with technology.

The weakness of the bureaucracy in accelerating changes towards a digital bureaucracy is the existence of various regulations and mandates and mental attitudes (mental blocks) in each agency. A fellow South Korean diplomat who has served in Jakarta and provided consulting assistance related to the development of e-government in Indonesia explained the importance of the Digital Government Law to eliminate various regulatory obstacles in transforming the digital bureaucracy. This law becomes a kind of Omnibus Law of Digital Governance to integrate various sectoral regulations related to various business processes and agency mandates. In addition, there is uncertainty as to whom the implementing agency has the authority to carry out the digital transformation of the Indonesian bureaucracy. Several ministries (such as the Ministry of Communication and Informatics and the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform) have regulatory authority, but it has no authority of execution.

In some countries, there is a kind of Digital Transformation Implementing Agency (for example, in Australia, there is a Digital Transformation Agency) that is given full authority to implement various policies in the context of digital transformation. A digital transformation implementing agency needs to be established in Indonesia or give authority to certain Non-Ministerial Government Institutions with the personnel and institutional capacity to carry out digital transformation. Finally, of course, we do not need to worry. The children of the Indonesian nation can master IT technology, robotics, AI, and others that can benefit the nation and state. The government only needs to build an ecosystem for the growth and development of this innovation.

6.4. Bureaucratic Transformation

The rapid development of society must be able to be responded to by the bureaucracy by transforming from within. The term transformation comes from the words transform: to change in composition, structure, or character, and transformation: an act, process, or instance of transforming or being transformed (Time, 1978:565). The term transformation indicates the existence of an activity to change something, its composition, structure, and character. With the understanding of transformation, bureaucratic transformation is related to the internal condition of the bureaucracy, namely in implementing functions and duties as a public servant.

Implementing bureaucratic functions and duties reflects two sides that are squeezed and influence each other. The bureaucracy can be seen from the side of the "apparatus," individuals who carry out their duties and functions, and as institutions that show institutions that carry out functions with specific procedures. Until now, there is still a stigma in society toward bureaucracy. As Albrow (Rachbini, 2002: 124) points out in a negative perspective, e.g., the bureaucracy is the authority or power which various government departments and their branches arrogate to themselves over their fellow citizens. Bureaucracy is a power in which government departments and branches are haughty towards the wider community. The stigma inherent in implementing bureaucratic tasks must be addressed by the government with innovative efforts so that the positive role of the bureaucracy is strengthened. The importance of this paradigm shift is inseparable from the existence of rapidly changing external conditions. There are four main reasons stated by Siagian (1994: 104), namely:

First, without any competition in producing certain products or services, the government bureaucracy must work quickly, at least to meet the increasing demands of society. Second, due to the limited ability of the government to provide work facilities and infrastructure for all its officials, the government bureaucracy is required to work with the highest possible level of efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity that will not be realized if the officials work slowly. Third, their primary duties must work quickly and continue on standby in certain aspects of society, nation, and state life, such as ensuring the state's safety, territorial integrity, and government apparatus. Fourth, in the era of globalization, as it is today, a state government in a particular field does compete with other governments and countries.

Strictly speaking, the above statement that it is essential and urgent to change the position and role of the bureaucracy is often identified with negative things into an organ that works by the demands and needs of a massively growing society. It is in line with Lawrence & Lorch (Thoha, 1995: 172) that the organic form of bureaucracy should be changeable and well-suited for complex and erratic environmental situations. Communication advancement and information technology it does require the bureaucracy to have the speed of transforming itself to work according to the standards needed by the public. It is inseparable from the fact that the development and increase in people's needs are speedy. On the other hand, the government bureaucracy tends to change more slowly, whereas, as acknowledged by B. Guy Peters (Rasyid, 1997, p. 44), bureaucratic empire-building is only partially related to the desire of the bureaucracy itself to survive. It also relates to the development of functions seen as essential to benefit the community's quality of life. Thus, it clearly shows the crush of bureaucratic interests to transform themselves with the fulfillment of the needs and interests of society.

6.5. Individual Factors

From the individual side, the effort needed is to change attitudes and self-views in the context of carrying out functions. Many changes have to do with the mental attitude of the bureaucratic apparatus. The most significant change in the bureaucracy is the way of looking at its functions and duties. It must lead to professionalism, that is, seeing duties as responsibilities and obligations as a consequence of the position as servants of society. Professional Working means that a person understands the ins and outs of his duties. Thus, the capable can carry out the task as well as possible (Siagian, 1994: 123). That is, understanding responsibilities and obligations are essential. Bureaucratic officials must realize that consciously they work to serve the public. In carrying out its duties of being responsible to the public, the government bureaucracy is closely related to human behavior as an element of bureaucracy in the organizational structure of government, both the behavior of individuals in formal and informal groups, as well as the internal and external behavior of government organization (Supriatna, 1997, pp. 100-101). Thus, every task carried out is not only formally accountable to superiors or government agencies but must realize that the performance of the task has implications for the public interest. In addition, there must be a change in perspective and attitude in interpreting positions. That the position held by a bureaucratic officer must be viewed in the context of authority means inherent authority. As stated by Surbakti (1992: 90), if an authorized person or acting person claims the right to govern by showing a procedural or substantial basis of authority, then members of the governed community have certain attitudes towards authority. It often happens that the bureaucratic apparatus is incapable and unwilling to separate the situation between affairs related to office and those outside the position. This condition triggers abuse of power. Transforming the bureaucratic apparatus will affect their positional perspective on society. Serving the community no longer has a negative

meaning. On the contrary, it becomes something positive because it serves as a form of responsibility as a servant of the state and a dignified servant of society.

Institutional Factors

Institutionally, several aspects need to be considered by the internal government to improve the quality of work of the bureaucracy so that it will directly or indirectly positively affect the implementation of its functions and duties. An essential aspect of the government is to streamline the implementation of duties and authorities by carrying out a working system that allows every bureaucratic apparatus to realize its responsibilities through the ability to carry out tasks. As for the mechanism that must be used through the carrot and stick approach, Kwik Kian Gie (Tanthowi et al., 2005, p. 167) states:

"Carrot is concerned with the net income of civilian employees and those in the military and police, sufficient to meet his standard of living commensurate with his education, expertise, leadership, level, and position. If necessary, his opinion is made high so that he is not only able to live decently but also enough to live "honorable." Stick regarding punishment, when all its needs can be met, and people are still committing corruption, it should be given harsh punishment because there is no more reason to carry out acts of corruption."

Kwik Kian Gie illustrates the importance of establishing norms that every bureaucratic apparatus must obey in carrying out their duties and functions. With rewards and penalties in assessing bureaucratic performance, it is hoped that it can improve the performance of the government bureaucracy. These efforts have now begun to be carried out by the government with the existence of measures or performance standards in the "reward" system popularly known as performance allowance. On the other hand, if the bureaucratic apparatus does not meet the established work standards, it will get sanctions in the form of delays and even the elimination of performance benefits.

In addition, there must be a change in how bureaucratic institutions interpret public servants quickly and accurately by shortening and facilitating public services through changes in centralized services to decentralization. Undeniably, the need for speed and accuracy in implementing bureaucratic functions and tasks is a reality that must be faced. It is inseparable from the increasing mobility of the community, so speed and accuracy are essential measures in solving problems. Therefore, the government bureaucracy must be able to follow the dynamics that exist in society—improving the performance of the government bureaucracy through shortening and simplifying functions and tasks, especially those that touch the interests of the community. Efforts need to be made to change the authority that has been centralized so that it takes a long time to decentralize authority by the classical theory called the Law of Arms and Fingers (Ndraha, 2003, p. 191). A formula is deduced from the law: the Short Arm Long Finger (SALF) and the Long Arm Short Finger (LASF). SALF theory shows a centralization model that results in the length and duration of the process so that the burden of bureaucracy, especially those on the frontlines, is burdened in carrying out their functions and duties. The SALF model, on the other hand, shows that there is a short process, and it takes a short time so that the bureaucracy can carry out its functions and tasks efficiently and effectively.

The theory wants to show the importance of decentralization of authority so that the bureaucracy is easier and more flexible in carrying out its duties and functions. The objective reason for the importance of decentralization of authority, as stated by Osborne & Gaebler (1999: 283-284) that decentralized institutions have several advantages: "First, decentralized institutions are much more flexible than centralized ones, they can respond quickly to changing environments and customer needs; Second, decentralized institutions are much more effective than centralized ones; Third, decentralized institutions are much more innovative than centralized ones; Fourth, decentralized institutions result in higher morale, more commitment, and greater productivity."

The above arguments show the connection between the bureaucracy's institutional transformation and the speed and accuracy of its tasks and functions. Through decentralization, bureaucratic authority becomes more flexible, not shackled by formal rules and long hierarchical structures, so it can function as a public service as expected by the community.

7. Conclusion

Factually, the government bureaucracy must develop itself to adjust to the increasingly high public expectations for running bureaucratic functions and duties, especially as public servants. Through the explanation above, several things can be concluded:

- 1) The government bureaucracy as an organ of government has the primary and essential function of providing services to the community. With the increasing demands of the community for quality services, especially the speed and accuracy of services, the bureaucracy, both individually and institutionally, must strive to transform itself.
- 2) It is necessary to make efforts to change from within the bureaucratic body itself, both changes from the individual aspect, namely the bureaucratic apparatus, by changing attitudes and perspectives in carrying out duties, especially in terms of seeing work professionally, namely as a responsibility and integrity. In addition, there is accountability for the public.
- 3) Institutionally, bureaucratic transformation is implemented strictly through rewards and punishments. It also changed from centralization of authority to decentralization of authority.

References

- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. In Vicki Knight (Ed.), *Intercultural Education* (Third Edit, Vol. 20, Issue 2). SAGE Publications Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675980902922143>
- Dumalang, G. V. (2021). Adaptive, Agile, and Innovative Key to Superior HR. *Journal of Public Administration*, 17(2), 175–196. <https://doi.org/10.52316/jap.v17i2.84>
- Firdaus, I. T., Tursina, M. D., & Roziqin, A. (2021). Digital Bureaucratic Transformation During the Covid-19 Pandemic to Realize the Digitalization of Indonesian Government in the study " The Microsoft Asia Digital Transformation: Enabling The Intelligent President Joko Widodo at a Limited Meeting on Planning Tr. Kybernan: *Journal of Government Studies*, 4(2), 226–239.
- Fukuyama, M. (2018). Society 5.0: Aiming for a New Human-centered Society. *Japan SPOTLIGHT*, 2(1)(August), 8–13.
- Holmqvist, M., & Pessi, K. (2006). Agility through scenario development and continuous implementation: A global aftermarket logistics case. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 15(2), 146–158. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000602>
- Ismail. (2019). Government Governance in the Industrial. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 9(2), 218–230.
- Jovanovski, T., & Muric, M. (2011). The phenomenon of lag in the application of the measures of monetary policy. *Economist Istrazivanja*, 24(2), 154–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2011.11517463>
- Muhammad, Ismail, et al.(2018). *Government Agency Performance Accountability System Module*, LAN RI, Jakarta
- Munier, N., Hontoria, E., & Jiménez-Sáez, F. (2019). *Strategic Approach in Multi-Criteria Decision Making* (Vol. 275).
- Ndraha, T. (2003). *Kybernology (New Government Science) Volumes 1- 2*. Jakarta : Rineka Cipta
- Oktari, Rosi. (2020). Are You Ready to Be the Golden Generation of 2045? (Online), <https://indonesiabaik.id/infografis/siapkah-kamu-jadi-generasi--emas-2045>. Retrieved 3 March 2021
- Osborne, D., & Ted Gaebler. (1999). *Entrepreneurship of Bureaucracy*, (Translation of Muhammad Rosyid), Binaman Pressindo Library, Jakarta
- Özdemir, V., & Hekim, N. (2018). Birth of Industry 5.0: Making Sense of Big Data with Artificial Intelligence, "the Internet of Things" and Next-Generation Technology Policy. *OMICS A Journal of Integrative Biology*, 22(1), 65–76. <https://doi.org/10.1089/omi.2017.0194>
- Prasojo, E. (2021). Building a Digital Bureaucracy. Faculty of Administrative Sciences, University of Indonesia, September 1–20. <https://fia.ui.ac.id/membangun-birokrasi-digital/>
- Priyono, H. (1995). *Dimensions of Discipline In Government Bureaucracy*. Jakarta
- Rachbini, Didi J. (2002). *Political Economy Paradigm and Theory of Public Choice*, Ghalia Indonesia, Jakarta
- Rasyid, Muhammad Ryaas. (1997). *The Meaning of Governance Review In Terms of Ethics and Leadership*, Rismawan, W. (2018). Strategic Management of Bureaucracy in the Era of Disruption. *Dynamics: Scientific Journal of State Administrative Sciences*. Vol 5 No 4. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25157/dinamika.v5i4.1748>
- Sawir, M. (2020). *Public Service Bureaucracy: Concepts, Theories, and Applications*. Deepublish Publishers, Sleman, Yogyakarta

- Schwab, K. (2016). The Fourth Industrial Revolution (World Economic Forum (ed.)).
<https://www.ptonline.com/articles/how-to-get-better-mfi-results>
- Serpa, S., & Ferreira, C. M. (2019). The Concept of Bureaucracy by Max Weber. *International Journal of Social Science Studies*, 7(2), 12. <https://doi.org/10.11114/ijsss.v7i2.3979>
- Siagian, Sondang P.(1994). *Bureaucratic Pathology Analysis of Its Identification and Therapy*, Ghalia Indonesia, Jakarta
- Supriatna, T. (1997). *The bureaucracy of Empowerment and Poverty Alleviation*. London: Humanities Main Press.
- Surbakti, Ramlan. (1992). *Understanding Political Science*, Gramedia, Jakarta
- Tanthowi, Pramono U. et al. (ed). (2005). *Eradicating the Cancer of Corruption*, PSAP, Jakarta.
- Thoha, M. (1995). *Indonesian Bureaucracy in the Era of Globalization*, Batang Gadis, Jakarta
- Time. (1978). *Webster's New Ideal Dictionary*. G & Merriam Co., Philippines